

SITE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1504 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic		Cabin #
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In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: ~~829-30~~ Photo Model: Yes No #: 355

DEFINITION
Two Tufo blocks near threshold

Covered by SU: ? Fills: SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX														
☐ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>☐ Hard</td> <td>☐ Black ☐ Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☐ Compact</td> <td>☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☐ Friable</td> <td>☐ Light Gray ☐ White</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☐ Loose</td> <td>☐ Yellow ☐ Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☐ Soft</td> <td>☐ Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>☐ Other (specify)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	☐ Hard	☐ Black ☐ Brown	☐ Compact	☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown	☐ Friable	☐ Light Gray ☐ White	☐ Loose	☐ Yellow ☐ Red	☐ Soft	☐ Light Yellow		☐ Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by:	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
Feature was exposed in 2011, but not issued a SU number. Cleared & documented first week of 2012 season

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: *South-west area B, just north of threshold*
Shape: *L-shape*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight</p> <p>Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

96cm l x 16cm wide x 16cm high

Description:

Two Dark Grey tufo
blocks, ca. 16cm wide,
of differing lengths

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Unknown Function. Placed close to threshold + possibly related, but on a slightly different orientation. Still, perhaps represents the northern limit of some very small foyer.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filed-out by SIFARR

on 82-6-12

Revised by

on

PDFd by

on

Entered by

on